

Recommended Practices on Lidar-assisted Control of Floating Wind Turbines

VAMOS Project (Validation,
Measurement and Optimization
of Floating Wind Energy Systems)

Supported by:

Federal Ministry
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and Climate Action

on the basis of a decision
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Authors

Feng Guo
Frank Lemmer
David Schlipf
Steffen Raach

Reviewed by
Steffen Raach

Approved by
Steffen Raach

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The VAMOS Project

The VAMOS (Validation, Measurement and Optimization of Floating Wind Energy Systems) project is a collaborative project funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag. The main objective of the VAMOS project is to close knowledge gaps in the measurement and simulation of floating offshore wind energy system for commercial use.

The partners, University of Stuttgart, Hamburg University of Technology and engineering consultant sowento GmbH, collaborate with the French platform manufacturer BW Ideol on their FLOAT-GEN prototype at the SEM-REV test site for a period of 36 months.

The project covers full-scale measurements, numerical modeling, control and optimization of a floating offshore wind energy system. The dynamic behavior of the floating wind turbine prototype were reproduced numerically by models of different levels of detail. Two Lidar systems were installed on the prototype for a measurement campaigns to obtain the power curve, perform wake measurements and develop knowledge in lidar measurements on floating wind turbines. The nacelle-mounted Lidar will be used to validate methods to obtain the power curve. The wake measurements, on the other side, will be used to validate aerodynamic models, which can reproduce the wake behind the turbine.

Universität Stuttgart

TUHH

Technische Universität Hamburg

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1 Introduction

The development of floating wind turbines has opened new spaces of designing and operating wind turbines. Because of the floating platform, the entire system faces more motions and experiences interactions not only with the wind, but also with the hydrodynamics with the waves and current, and the mooring lines.

This report gives recommendations on transferring lidar-assisted control technology from bottom-fixed wind turbines to floating wind turbines and gives an example evaluation of the impact on the performance of the floating wind turbine.

The report starts by presenting the problems of applying lidar-based wind field reconstruction on floating wind turbines and indicates the key solutions to the problem by comparing different wind field reconstruction methods. Secondly, lidar-assisted control strategies of different technology maturity levels are presented. The improvements required for higher-maturity technologies for floating applications are presented. Lastly, this report assesses the benefits of lidar-assisted control using one of the technically more mature strategies, namely lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback control, considering a 15 MW floating turbine.

Figure 1: The nacelle-based lidar installed on the FLOATGEN prototype, measuring the inflowing wind.

2 Background

This Chapter provides executive summaries about lidar-assisted turbine control and the control challenge of floating wind turbines.

2.1 Lidar-assisted control of wind turbines

Lidar is a remote-sensing technology that can provide a preview of the incoming turbulent wind [1]. Lidar-assisted control (LAC) integrates lidar wind preview into the control system, allowing for advanced control algorithms such as pitch feedforward and model predictive controls [2, 3, 1].

sowento has 15 years of experience in the field of lidar-assisted control. Back in 2008, research and testing of lidar-assisted control started at the University of Stuttgart. Since then, David Schlipf, head of the Lidar Technology at sowento, has built up experience on lidar data processing and advanced lidar-assisted control technologies. His pioneering work in the field of lidar-assisted control has shaped sowento and is a key business of the company. In 2016, sowento was founded by David Schlipf, Florian Haizmann, Steffen Raach, Holger Fürst, and Frank Lemmer with the aim of providing advanced control solutions and the latest simulation techniques to the wind industry. Nowadays, sowento works on lidar-assisted control, advanced wind field reconstruction, and modeling, coupled-analysis, and controller design for floating wind turbines with their partners.

Thus far, collective pitch feedforward control has now been deployed in commercial projects [4] because of its simplicity and ease of integration with existing feedback control systems. sowento has supported Goldwind to implement lidar-assisted collective pitch feedforward control in 2018. According to publicly available information, more than 1000 commercial onshore turbines manufactured by Goldwind are now operating with LAC [5]. Recently, Goldwind erected the first GWH 230-9.0 MW prototype turbine, in which LAC technology is deployed¹.

Lidar-assisted control is a multidisciplinary subject. It requires a good understanding of lidar measurement principles, turbulence characteristics, signal processing, and turbine control. The lidar system relies on the Doppler effect, and it measures the line-of-sight (LOS) wind speed, which is the projection of a three-dimensional wind velocity vector in the laser beam direction [6]. However, the turbine's aerodynamics are primarily contributed by the longitudinal wind components distributed among the rotor-swept area, whose average value is usually referred to as the rotor effective wind speed (REWS). Especially, the nacelle motion of floating turbines is considerable and it also contributes to the LOS measurement [7]; therefore, an advanced wind field reconstruction technique with motion compensation is required to obtain a good estimation of the REWS. In addition, because the turbine blades have large spatial operations, the rotor aerodynamic torque or thrust force is mainly contributed by the spatially coherent turbulence structures, i.e., the low-frequency part of the turbulence. The typical commercial lidar system provides LOS speed measurements from several beam directions at upstream positions. The limited measurement positions, the evolution of turbulence from upstream to downstream, and the contamination by non-longitudinal wind components all lead to imperfect estimation of REWS by lidar systems [6]. The imperfection caused by the phenomena above is reflected as the high-frequency components in

¹<https://www.goldwind.com/cn/news/focus-article?id=784813904919402496> In Chinese.

the lidar-estimated REWS, which is uncorrelated with the actual REWS experienced by the turbine rotor. Nevertheless, the low-frequency spatially coherent structures still can be measured by lidar systems, and they can be obtained by filtering the lidar-estimated REWS [8].

With the wind speed preview provided by a lidar system, the feedforward blade pitch controller can be designed for alleviating the changes in aerodynamic torque or the aerodynamic thrust force [1, 7, 8]. For the above-rated wind speed conditions, the adjustment in blade pitch angles affects both the torque and thrust. For typical turbine designs, increasing blade pitch angles reduces both aerodynamic torque and thrust, and vice versa. For FOWT, if the pitch feedforward control is designed to alleviate the change in aerodynamic torque, special attention should be paid to the frequency range close to the natural frequency of the platform pitch mode. A reduction in aerodynamic torque comes with a decrease in rotor thrust, and therefore the platform moves forward. As a consequence, the relative wind speed seen by the turbine is higher than the free-stream wind speed predicted by the lidar system, and the rotor speed regulation close to the platform's natural frequency is usually not satisfied. A typical solution to this problem can be multivariable feedback controllers, which will be explained in the next section. On the other hand, if the pitch forward control is designed for alleviating thrust force change, a good regulation of the platform pitch motion can be achieved, as shown by [9]. In this context, a very flexible adjustment of the generator torque is required to compensate for the aerodynamic torque changes. A more complex LAC design is the non-linear model predictive control (MPC). In this technology, trajectories for collective pitch and the generator torque are real-time optimized within a time window that fulfills all desired constraints and controller goals [10, 11].

2.2 Control of floating wind turbines

The task of controller design for the FOWT is particularly critical due to the potential "negative damping" of the FOWT in platform pitch mode which has been reported repeatedly. An intuitive explanation of the negative damping effect can be as follows. For the above-rated operations, an increment in the wind speed accelerates the rotor and the standard proportional-integral (PI) controller commands a larger pitch angle to reduce aerodynamic torque. However, at the same time, the rotor thrust force decreases and the floating turbine moves forward. This forward motion induces a larger wind speed, which further accelerates the rotor. With frequency response analysis, this negative damping is due to a transfer zero from blade pitch angle to rotor speed in the right half-plane [12, 13].

Several controller design approaches have been investigated to tackle the negative damping issue. On the one hand, the PI controller can be detuned to reduce bandwidth, in order not to excite the right half-plane zeros [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]. The detuned PI controller, however, has several side effects, e.g. the regulation of the rotor speed is often unsatisfactory. It leads to large rotor speed, power, and drivetrain load fluctuations and causes a higher probability of undesired over-speed events. On the other hand, multivariable controllers help to improve controller performance. These controllers feedback not only one rotor speed signal but tower-top or platform motion signals for improved platform damping [19, 20, 3, 21, 22, 23, 18, 24]. Such multivariable controllers are often state feedback controllers, which require measurements of all states of the controller design model.

Figure 2 shows a comparison of the ratio of controller bandwidth divided by the rated rotor speed in the above-rated conditions for different turbine ratings, all on floating foundations. The controller

bandwidth can be interpreted as an indicator of the performance of rotor speed tracking. A higher bandwidth means a more aggressive PI controller tuning which allows better tracking of the rated speed. The bandwidth for FOWTs, as discussed above, has to be limited by the natural frequency of the platform pitch mode. For a larger turbine size, the relative controller bandwidth is increased, as we have shown in [25], and the rated speed decreases further. Therefore, the bandwidth divided by the rated rotor speed increases. Overall, the "negative damping" problem exists for the IEA 15MW FOWT.

As the aerodynamic thrust increases quadratically with the blade radius, wind loads become increasingly dominant for large FOWT, such that advanced lidar-assisted control solutions are promising [26].

Figure 2: Comparison of possible controller bandwidth for 5, 10 and 15MW FOWTs. Bandwidth is usually limited by the platform pitch natural frequency of the FOWT.

3 Recommendations for lidar data processing

For lidar-assisted turbine control, the lidar data processing is a key step which converts lidar measurements to usable control signals. This Chapter provides recommendations for lidar data processing (LDP) that require additional attention for the application of lidar-assisted control on floating wind turbines.

3.1 Measurement of floating wind turbine-mounted nacelle lidar

Overall, the LDP for turbine control includes two steps. The first step is called wind field reconstruction (WFR) by which the longitudinal wind component is estimated from the LOS speed measurement. The second step estimates the REWS from the longitudinal wind components by the first step. The first step is significantly demanding for floating turbine applications.

To better illustrate the two steps, we start by explaining the measurement of floating turbine-mounted nacelle lidar. As shown by Figure 3, the nacelle-lidar mounted on a floating turbine has two negative impacts caused by the nacelle motion. First, the translational velocity of the lidar contribute to the Doppler effect whose contribution is included in the lidar LOS speed measurement. Second, the motion causes more significant misalignment compared to onshore bottom-fixed turbines. Note that, in Figure 3, the inertial and lidar coordinate systems are denoted by subscript “ \mathcal{I} ” and “ \mathcal{L} ”, respectively. Overall, neglecting the probe volume effect, the lidar LOS wind speed measurement can be approximated by

$$v_{\text{LOS}} = (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}_{\text{L}}) \cdot \mathbf{n}. \quad (3.1)$$

where $\mathbf{n} = [x_{n,\mathcal{I}}, y_{n,\mathcal{I}}, z_{n,\mathcal{I}}]$ is a unit vector that aligns in lidar beam direction defined in the inertial coordinate system. \mathbf{u} is the wind velocity vector and \mathbf{v}_{L} is the translational velocity vector of the lidar system, both defined in the inertial coordinate system.

To show the importance of motion compensation for lidar-assisted floating turbine control, we define three wind field reconstruction techniques with different complexities and compare their performances on LAC of a floating 15 MW turbine.

3.2 Baseline wind field reconstruction without motion compensation

This baseline method (hereafter denoted as WFR1) is typically used for the bottom-fixed turbine. Because nacelle lidar’s beam opening angles are usually designed to be small with respect to the longitudinal direction, the contribution of non-longitudinal wind components to the LOS speed (v_{LOS}) is much smaller than that of the longitudinal components. Therefore, it is reasonable to ignore the non-longitudinal wind components and estimate the longitudinal wind component by [27]:

$$\hat{u} = v_{\text{LOS}}/x_{n,\mathcal{L}}, \quad (3.2)$$

where $x_{n,\mathcal{L}}$ is the first element of a unit vector aligning in the lidar beam direction within the lidar coordinate system. Also, this baseline WFR assumes that the lidar is perfectly aligned with the longitudinal (mean wind) direction, as indicated by the left part of Figure 3. Therefore, $x_{n,\mathcal{L}}$ is unchanged if the lidar beam direction is fixed.

Figure 3: The impact of floating turbine motion on the lidar measurement. The inertial and lidar coordinate systems are denoted by subscript “ \mathcal{I} ” and “ \mathcal{L} ”, respectively.

3.3 Wind field reconstruction by motion compensation with orientation measurement

With this approach (hereafter denoted as WFR2), the translational velocity of the lidar system is ignored but the real-time orientation provided by an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) is considered. Therefore, the the longitudinal wind component is estimated by

$$\hat{u} = (v_{\text{LOS}})/x_{n,\mathcal{I}}. \quad (3.3)$$

Here, instead of $x_{n,\mathcal{L}}$, $x_{n,\mathcal{I}}$ is used to account for the real-time misalignment caused by turbine motion.

3.4 Wind field reconstruction by motion compensation with velocity measurement

In this approach (hereafter denoted as WFR3), the misalignment of the lidar system with the inertial coordinate system is still ignored. The real-time lidar transnational velocity measurement by an IMU are used to estimate the longitudinal wind component by

$$\hat{u} = (v_{\text{LOS}} + \mathbf{v}_L \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{L}})/x_{n,\mathcal{L}}. \quad (3.4)$$

Here, the unit vector $\mathbf{n}_{\mathcal{L}} = [x_{n,\mathcal{L}}, y_{n,\mathcal{L}}, z_{n,\mathcal{L}}]$ aligns in lidar beam direction in the lidar local coordinate system, as shown in Figure 3

3.5 Wind field reconstruction by motion compensation with orientation and velocity measurements

The fourth method (hereafter denoted as WFR4) requires both real-time rotational angles and transnational velocity measurement of the lidar, which applies the equation below

$$\hat{u} = (v_{\text{LOS}} + \mathbf{v}_L \cdot \mathbf{n})/x_{n,\mathcal{I}}, \quad (3.5)$$

to fully compensate the negative effects of turbine motion.

The WFR4 method has been tested through the “smart lidar” project within the scope of VAMOS. Figure 5 compares the spectra of the lidar-estimated REWS derived from the measured data and the analytical model. The lidar data are collected from a four-beam pulsed lidar manufactured by Leosphere, which is mounted on the FLOATGEN prototype floating turbine. As indicated by the green lines, the base line LDP (WFR1) has a spectral peak at around 0.1 Hz, which is dominant frequency of wave height variation. At this frequency, the platform motion caused by wave height changes contributes to the lidar motion and is mistakenly recognized as wind speed by the baseline LDP. With the full MC (WFR4), as shown by the blue line, the peak associated with wave height is eliminated. However, because of the blade blockage effect, the lidar measurement is not continuously available. As a consequence, the estimated REWS can include the error due to non-eventually distributed available LOS speeds among the vertical direction. For example, for a four-beam lidar system, the estimated REWS can be higher than the actual value if one of the lower beam is blocked while the rest are not. These causes additional REWS spectra at frequency higher than 0.1 Hz. Overall, the WFR problems associated with blade blockage is refereed as “Blade Ghost”. sowento has developed advanced WFR algorithms that avoids the negative impacts of Blade Ghost phenomenon. The orange line indicates the result after applying blade ghost avoidance algorithm, which highly agree with the analytical spectra of lidar-estimated REWS. The method of calculating the analytical spectrum has been summarized by [28, 8].

Figure 4: Comparisons of lidar-estimated REWS spectra. Source: [29].

To clearly show the difference between the three WFR methods above in terms of the lidar-assisted control performances, Figure 5 plots some key variables under an Extreme Operating Gust (EOG). The simulations are performed using a single-beam lidar towards the longitudinal direction and the IEA 15 MW offshore wind turbine on the UMaine VoltturnUS-S semi-submersible floating platform [30, 31]. Here, no waves are included. The ROSCO controller [32] is considered as the baseline feedback-only control. The details about the used controller are discussed further in Section 4.1. The platform feedback loop is disabled. We have assumed a perfect IMU in the simulation which provides a perfect measurement of rotational angles (orientations) and translational velocities for the lidar system.

In the first row, the actual REWS is plotted. In the second row, the differences between REWSs estimated by the four WFR methods and the actual REWS are shown. Here, the lidar-estimated REWSs are shifted according to their leading time before calculating the difference. It is clear that WFR1 and WFR2 are very similar, with both predicting REWS with increasing error over time. Oppositely, WFR3 and WFR4, both with velocity compensation, are in good agreement, and they accurately predict the actual REWS.

The rest rows show the control variable and the output variables. The results by WFR3 and WFR4 are almost equal. In all WFR cases, the variations in the rotor speed are significantly suppressed since the aerodynamic torques are well predicted by the lidar-assisted control loop. In the case of WFR1 without MC and WFR2 with orientation correction only, the velocity of platform motion is mistakenly recognized as REWS estimation and it is then used for unnecessary blade pitch actions. As a consequence, the system is unstable. With WFR3 and WFR4, the platform pitch amplitude (max-min) is reduced by -63.5% compared to that using feedback-only control.

The only difference between WFR1 and WFR2 is the consideration of misalignment, and the main differences between WFR1 and WFR3 and between WFR2 and WFR4 are the inclusion of velocity compensation. Based on this example, the lessons learned are that motion compensation is vital for lidar-assisted control of floating wind turbines. To set up the motion compensation, it is especially important to give the lidar system accurate measurements of the translational velocity.

Figure 5: Comparison of different WFR methods in terms of feedforward control performances towards an EOG.

4 Recommendations for the adaptation of controllers

This Chapter introduces four lidar-assisted feedforward control techniques that have different level of complexities. The first one is the baseline lidar-assisted controller typically used for onshore applications. This technique is already applied to commercial onshore turbine. The adaptations regarding this type of controller for floating application is discussed. Then, the second controller, namely lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable, adds another floating feedback loop on top of the first controller which aims for provide more damping to the platform pitch motion. Thirdly, lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward controller is discussed which utilize both blade pitch and generator torque as feedforward signals. Lastly, the lidar-assisted model predict control is introduced which solves online optimization problem in time domain to get desired control inputs.

4.1 Baseline lidar-assisted controller for floating wind turbines

For bottom fixed turbines, the common and industrially verified design is lidar-assisted control for aerodynamic torque compensation. In this approach, the pitch feedforward loop is tuned based on the steady-state blade pitch curve. Ideally, it aims to adjust aerodynamic torque by blade pitching in advance so that less rotor speed acceleration or deceleration is achieved. As discussed earlier, a change in aerodynamic torque comes with a variation in rotor thrust and therefore the platform moves forward or backward. As a result, the relative wind speed seen by the turbine is different from the upstream wind speed predicted by the lidar system. Thus, the rotor speed regulation and platform pitch motion at the frequency close to the platform's natural frequency is usually not satisfied.

To tackle this issue, a simple and straightforward approach is to apply a notch filter to the lidar-estimated REWS. The typical lidar-assisted control design only relies on a linear low-pass filter to filter high-frequency components in the REWS caused by limited measurement points, cross-contamination by non-longitudinal wind components, and turbulence evolution, etc [6]. In floating applications, the lidar-estimated REWS is first low-pass filtered and then notch filtered. The cutoff frequency of the notch filter can be placed at the natural frequency of the platform pitch mode.

Figure 6 shows the spectra estimated from the OpenFAST time series considering three control configurations. The time series are simulated using a single range gate four-beam pulsed lidar and the IEA 15MW floating reference turbine. The turbulent wind is assumed to be defined by the IEC class 1B [33] with a hub-height mean wind speed of 18 ms^{-1} . No waves are included. The spectra are estimated by averaging the time series from six independent turbulence realizations. It is clear that both FF controls help to reduce rotor speed variation at lower frequency ranges, as expected. Better performance is achieved by the utilization of the notch filter. As for the platform pitch motion, the FFFB control can be worse than the FB-only control if the notch filter is not applied. The feedback controller is tuned to be not reactive close to the platform pitch mode due to the negative damping effect. However, the FF control does not avoid the negative damping effect if the notch filter is neglected. Once the notch filter is applied, the FBFF control has a clear reduction in both rotor speed and platform pitch variations.

In bottom-fixed turbine cases, the notch filter can also be necessary if the tower fore-aft natural

Figure 6: Spectra of rotor speed and platform pitch under three control configurations. Simulated using a single range gate four-beam pulsed lidar and the IEA 15MW floating reference turbine. The grey dashed line indicates the natural frequency of the platform pitch motion. The floating feedback loop is not considered.

frequency locates at a frequency range where the low-pass filter has a relatively high magnitude. The main additional consideration with the notch filter is that it increases the phase (time) delay for frequencies lower than its cutoff frequency. When optimizing lidar trajectories for floating turbine control, this delay effect should be considered with special attention. Usually, the lidar system needs to measure at a farther distance upstream to provide enough leading time for pitch feedforward control.

4.2 Lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback controller

In the baseline lidar-assisted controller, the notch filter is necessary to avoid feedforward pitch actions close to the natural frequency of platform pitch mode. The task of alleviation pitch motions can be, however, taken by a multivariable feedback (MVFB) controller. It has been revealed that feeding the platform pitch angle [34] shows better control performances than feeding back the tower top motion signal. In MVFB control, the platform pitch rate is multiplied by a floating feedback gain to obtain a blade pitch angle. This loop is summed with the conventional PI pitch loop to obtain the overall blade pitch command. The role of the MVFB loop is to increase rotor thrust by reducing blade pitch angles when the FOWT moves forward, and vice versa. As a consequence, it acts like a damper to the FOWT pitch motion.

The MVFB control can be designed to band-pass the platform pitch rate signal only at the natural frequency of platform pitch mode. It can be combined with lidar-assisted control to achieve better overall control performance. Figure 7 shows the spectra estimated from the OpenFAST time series considering three control configurations. The only difference to the results presented by Figure 6

Figure 7: Spectra of rotor speed and platform pitch under three control configurations. Simulated using a single range gate four-beam pulsed lidar and the IEA 15MW floating reference turbine. The grey dashed line indicates the natural frequency of the platform pitch motion. The floating feedback loop is considered, with a gain constant of 9.4 s

is that the floating feedback loop is considered with a gain constant of 9.4 s. Compared to the results in Figure 6, both rotor speed and platform pitch variations are reduced considerably after introducing the feedback loop. By comparing FB-only with FFFB control, clear reductions of rotor speed and platform pitch variations are realized using LAC. Here, again, we prove the importance of the notch filter as better performances are achieved by the utilization of the notch filter in FBFF control.

4.3 Lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward controller.

The innovative lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward (MVFF) controller was proposed for regulating both the tower fore-aft motion and rotor speed of FOWTs [9]. In this approach, the first gain is designed to provide a feedforward pitch command that leads to zero acceleration of the tower top with respect to the changes in wind speed. A second gain is then designed to obtain a feedforward generator torque command that compensates for the changes in aerodynamic torque due to pitch actions linked to the first gain.

Figure 8 shows example time series by FB-only and FB+MVFF controls. The simulation was performed considering the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine mounted on the SWE-TripleSpar floating platform and a four-beam commercial lidar trajectory. The turbulence wind field corresponds to IEC class 1A, which has a mean wind speed of 16 m/s. Additionally, the irregular waves with a significant wave height of 3.7 m and a peak spectral period of 9.8 s are considered and simulated using the JONSWAP spectrum. The simulation is performed using a full aero-hydro-servo-elastic model in FAST. With FB+MVFF control, the variations in the rotor speed and platform pitch are reduced signif-

Figure 8: Comparison of time series using FB-only control and FB+MVFF control. Simulated using the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine mounted on the SWE-TripleSpar floating platform. Figure source: [9].

icantly. Additionally, the functions in platform surge and the tower top displacement are reduced. As summarized by [9], for the considered turbulence wave conditions, FB+MVFF control helps in load reduction for the tower base bending moment and blade root bending moment by almost 19 % and 25 %, respectively. However, large variations in the generator torque are observed with MVFF control. This places a higher demand on the ability to adjust the generator torque and leads to more fluctuations in aerodynamic forces.

4.4 Lidar-assisted model predictive controller

Since today's commercial lidar can measure LOS wind speeds at multiple upstream locations in front of the turbine rotor, it is possible to use advanced LDP techniques to estimate REWS over future time horizons. With this REWS time horizon, MPC becomes possible. The MPC algorithms determine the control inputs by solving an optimization problem, i.e., minimizing the cost function while not hitting the constraints. Utilization of the current state of the turbine system, the future disturbance (wind and wave), and the assumed control inputs, a reduced order model, which is capable to represent the main dynamics of the floating turbine system, predicts the future states within a certain time horizon. These predicted states and control inputs are linked to a cost function. For example, the cost function can be designed to minimize the weighted sum of variances of structure and actuator motions. In addition, certain constraints, such as the rotor speed limits, can be applied to the optimization algorithm. The lidar-assisted MPC continuously solves the optimization problem online; therefore, the control performance can be ideal if the future disturbance and the states are well predicted by the lidar and the reduced-order model, respectively.

Currently, there are several simulation studies that illustrated the benefits of lidar-assisted MPC [10, 11, 35]. These studies have shown that MPC is promising for the control of floating wind turbines due to its superior performance in regulating rotor speed and reducing load.

However, until today, to the authors' knowledge, no lidar-assisted MPC has been applied to commercial turbines, even bottom-fixed ones. The main challenges for the application of lidar-assisted MPC are listed below:

- Lidar-assisted MPC includes all the complexity of a baseline LAC problem for floating turbine. In addition, it requires a more complex LDP to provide a REWS prediction over a moving time horizon.
- The reduced-order modeling of FOWT for MPC is already a challenging task. It depends on the floater type and the mooring system design.
- There are difficulties in optimization process. The optimization space can be non-convex and might hit local minimal value.
- Uncertainties in lidar wind preview present and it is still not clear how to schedule lidar-assisted MPC based on the imperfect wind preview provided by lidar systems.
- The robustness and reliability of lidar-assisted MPC still need further verification.

5 Recommendations for implementation and validation steps

In previous Chapters, we discussed the adaptations that need to be made for the application of lidar-assisted control to floating wind turbines. A flow chart summarizing the main steps for validation is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The flow chart of recommended implementation and validation steps.

With the following text, we provide detailed procedures that are advised for the implementation and validation of floating lidar-assisted control in the future:

1. The coherence between lidar-estimated REWS and the turbine REWS can be further validated. Currently, the spectrum of lidar-estimated REWS using motion compensation is verified to be in agreement with the theoretical spectrum of REWS represented by turbulence spectral models for the FLOATGEN turbine. For different turbine sizes, the spatial separations are different. Therefore, further validation of turbulence models or parameters can be carried on using lidar measurement mounted on a large rotor turbine that has large spatial separations in all three-spatial directions. The turbine REWS can be estimated using techniques such as the Kalman filter using turbine signals. In this step, the analysis of the phase differences between the two REWSs is also essential. Because the notch filter causes further phase delays for lidar-estimated REWS, a large longitudinal separation upstream is required to provide enough leading time for feedforward control. Preferably, the analysis of phase difference should be performed for large longitudinal separations, such as 1.5 rotor diameter in front of the rotor.

2. Another step that can be tested in parallel with the previous step is a lidar data quality detection algorithm. Because lidar measurements may be unavailable if the carrier-to-noise ratio is too low, which occurs when backscatter intensity is low due to unusual weather patterns. In such conditions, the controller needs to switch to feedback-only control mode. When the availability of lidar measurements increases, the LAC can be faded in. Thus, a lidar data quality detection algorithm is recommended to be tested to provide a reliable lidar data quality indication.
3. After the previous steps have been done and proven to work, LAC for FOWT can be tested in the field, preferably on a full-size large-rotor turbine. In the beginning, testing of LAC can be made with reduced feedforward gains and full feedback gains. Data collected on site can be compared with simulation results to check if the field testing results agree with the expectations. Once the expectations are met, full feedforward gains can be activated. The full feedforward testing results should then be compared to the simulation results to verify if the implementation brings the expected benefits.
4. With all the previous steps being validated, testing with full feedforward gain and adaptive FB gain can be carried out. Depending on the lidar quality, the feedback gain needs to be scheduled. When lidar quality is high, the feedback gain can be less aggressive and let feedforward loop dominate the rotor speed regulation. Oppositely, the feedback gain should become more aggressive and dominate when lidar data quality is low.
5. The above steps aims for validating the baseline lidar-assisted feedforward control or the lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariate feedback control. If these tests are useful, one could aim for more complicate algorithms such as the lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward control or the model predictive control.

6 Evaluation of lidar-assisted control

This Chapter first presents the load performances of two control strategies for the IEA 15MW floating wind turbine. The Reference Open-Source Controller [36] is considered as the benchmark which is a multivariable feedback controller. A lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback controller is considered to investigate the benefits of lidar-preview control. Based on the performances, the possible impact on the design of floating wind turbines using the lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback control is discussed.

6.1 Performances on fatigue load reduction

We use the lidar-integrated OpenFAST version by [37] and perform simulations for DLC 1.2 specified by the IEC standard [33]. Instead of using the turbulence spectra parameters suggested by the IEC standard, we consider more realistic parameters based on offshore measurements by [38]. A Weibull distribution with shape and scale parameters equivalent to 2.02 and 9.41, respectively, are considered, which is based on the reanalysis data from a north sea site [39]. In these simulations, co-directional wind and wave are assumed, and only one wind and wave direction is

The used lidar system is a four-beam pulsed lidar with opening angles of 16° (with respect to the longitudinal wind direction). Its four beams are azimuthally evenly distributed in the rotor plane. Only the LOS measurements from the range gate 280 m upstream are used for feedforward control.

In order to evaluate the benefit of LAC, we consider the MVFB controller provided by the ROSCO toolbox [36] as the baseline controller. Then a lidar-assisted MVFB (FF+MVFB) controller whose feedback loops are re-tuned using the method presented by [40]. In general, with LAC, the rotor speed regulation is more relaxed and the tuning aims to minimize the tower-base loads while maintaining the maximum rotor speed within an acceptable threshold.

Figure 10 shows the Damage Equivalent Load (DEL), standard deviations (STD), and energy production (EP) of the IEA 15MW FOWT summarized from the DLC 1.2 simulations. The DELd calculated here is defined as the contribution of lifetime damage by each mean wind speed. The Wöhler exponents considered for blades, fairleads, and the rest components are 10, 3, and 4, respectively, considered. As for the SD and EP, the mean value calculated from the simulations by six different random seeds is presented.

Among the investigated fatigue loads, the most significant reduction by using LAC technology is in the tower base bending load, especially in mean wind speeds slightly higher than the rated wind speed (10.6 m/s). In addition, there are slight reductions in the blade, shaft, and mooring fairlead loads in this wind speed range. Compared to the baseline MVFB control, obviously fewer blade pitch actions, indicated by the blade pitch STD, are achieved by LAC in the mean wind speed from 10 to 14 m/s. While higher blade pitch actions are present at higher mean wind speeds. To further assess the pitch actuator damages, a more detailed pitch actuator load calculation would be required. In terms of the rotor speed and platform pitch, the utilization of LAC clearly reduces their STDs for above-rated mean wind speeds.

Table 1 further summarizes the DEL, extended lifetime (EL), and the AEP by the two controllers. The EL is defined as the extended lifetime by FF+MVFB control compared to the ROSCO baseline

Table 1: The lifetime (20 years) DEL, EL (in years), and AEP (in MWh) by the two control configurations.

	ROSCO MVFB	FF+MVFB retuned	$\frac{\text{FF+MVFB}}{\text{ROSCO MVFB}}$ [%]	EL [year]
TwrBsMyt	411.14	335.70	81.65	25.00
LSShftTq	3.69	3.59	97.18	2.43
RootMyb1	53.97	53.17	98.51	3.24
FAIRTEN1	1.15	1.08	93.76	4.26
FAIRTEN2	0.34	0.34	99.66	0.21
AEP	63718.87	63926.77	100.33	

MVFB controller. Again, significant load reduction or lifetime extension for the tower is achieved by LAC. The extended lifetime is even higher than the designed lifetime of 20 years. Slight reductions and lifetime extensions in the blade, shaft, and mooring fairlead loads are also obtained with LAC. In terms of AEP, a marginal increment is achieved by LAC, which is caused by the small EP increase close to rated wind speed, as shown in Figure 10.

6.2 Possible impact on the design of floating wind turbines

We show that LAC can significantly reduce fatigue load in the tower's fore-aft direction for the IEA 15MW submersible turbine. It also helps to reduce the fatigue load of the front mooring fairlead. These loads are highly linked to the rotor thrust force.

The significant reduction using LAC can lead to a new design of the tower. While, for FOWT design, the design needs to be evaluated systematically considering the coupling with the platform and mooring system. Therefore, integrated simulation environments and design processes considering LAC become important in the designing stage.

As the turbine design is not only driven by the fatigue load but by ultimate loads as well. Some studies in the literature have revealed the possibility to use a lidar system to distinguish the extreme turbulence conditions that are linked to ultimate loads. With this capability, the extreme loads can be reduced by derating the turbine during unusual turbulence levels.

If the extreme load can be limited, one possibility is to design the turbine to have a longer lifetime [41]. In such a case, the fatigue load becomes more dominant than the ultimate load because of longer cycles. Then, the advantage of fatigue load reduction by LAC can be more extraordinary.

Figure 10: DEL, STD, and EP of the IEA 15MW FOWT summarized from the DLC 1.2 simulations.

7 Conclusions

In this report, we propose recommended practices for lidar-assisted control of floating wind turbines.

Four different wind field reconstruction methods are compared that have different motion compensation considerations. Through aeroelastic simulations, the lidar-assisted control performances towards an extreme operating gust using the four motion compensation algorithms are compared. We illustrate that the translational velocity compensation is vital to achieving a desired control behavior, which indicates the importance of an accurate inertial measurement unit in floating turbine applications.

We then introduce four lidar-assisted feedforward control techniques for floating turbines. For the baseline lidar-assisted controller and the lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback controller, we reveal that it is important to include notch filtering nearby the natural frequency of the platform fore-aft pitch mode. As for the other two more advanced techniques: the lidar-assisted multivariable feedforward control and the lidar-assisted model predictive control, we summarize their benefits and associated challenges. Recommended implementation and validation steps for lidar-assisted floating turbine control are listed in detail.

The benefits of lidar-assisted control for the floating turbine are illustrated by the lidar-assisted feedforward and multivariable feedback control. The benefits are assessed through aeroelastic simulations considering the IEC design load case 1.2 for the IEA 15 MW floating turbine. Compared to a benchmark multivariable feedback controller, introducing lidar-assisted control reduces the lifetime tower base fore-aft bending load by around 18% and the fairlead tension load by around 6%.

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